

THE ROLE OF ISLOMKHODJA REFORMS IN THE TAX SYSTEM OF KHIVA KHANATE

Abdukhalilova A.E.

TSUOS PhD Student

baxtiyorovich91@bk.ru

+998911987868

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the analysis of the tax program imposed by Islamoja in the Khiva Khanate. The reform program adopted in 1910 was mainly focused on reforming the Khanate's tax system. The differentiated land tax, implemented under Muhammad Rahim Khan II, provided for the establishment of the solghut according to the amount of land, the abolition of tax incentives, labor obligations - the procedure for remuneration of yof Kazu. There were also plans to regulate the trade-industry tax - Zakat and duty tax.

Keywords. Asfandiyorkhan, manifest, tax, Islamkhoja, tax program, Kazu, qochu.

INTRODUCTION

For many years, in any period and in any country, the political situation by default requires reform of the tax system. The main goal of tax reform is also to achieve an acceptable balance between the stimulating and fiscal role of taxes. Tax reform is certainly being carried out in the state in order to equalize tax conditions, reduce the tax burden and simplify the tax system. At the same time, the tax administration system should ensure a reduction in the level of tax costs for both the state and taxpayers.

DISCUSSION

The Khanate of Khiva, which is an integral part of the history of Uzbekistan, has also undergone a number of tax reforms carried out by representatives of the Khukmran dynasty. One of them was implemented in 1806 by Muhammad Rahimkhan I (1806-1825) and provided for the introduction of a solgut instead of a land tax. Under this tax system, owners paid taxes in accordance with the category to which they belonged (alo, avso, adno), and not for the amount included in the top dressing¹.

Although the reform of Muhammad Rahim Khan I improved the socio-political life of the country for some time, by the beginning of the 20th century, the Khanate of Khiva found itself in a whirlpool of economic problems. Due to

¹ А. Абдухалилова XIX аср охири - XX асрнинг бошлари Хива хонлигида солиқ маъмурияти // Хоразм Маъмур Академияси ахборотномаси 12/2021.- Б.221-224

Russia's colonial policy, the Gandamian Peace Treaty was concluded, which stipulated that an equal half of the khanate would be transferred to the discretion of the empire. This led to the creation of the Amudarya Department and a reduction in the number of taxpayers. In addition, tax benefits for Russian merchants and the entry of the Khanate of Khiva into the unified customs line of the empire led to the economic rise of the Tanazuli state. The factors listed above have determined the need for reforms in the tax sector throughout the country.

THE MAIN PART

In 1910, the decree of Asfandiyarkhan was published, which provided for the regulation of state revenues. The issue of reform was seen as an instruction to citizens to calm down, live in prosperity, and solve social problems at the expense of funds. The execution of these works was entrusted to the Islamkhoja ibn Ibrokhimkhoja².

The event dedicated to the reform program presented to the Khan of Khiva by Prime Minister Islamkhoja was attended by A. Boltaev's contemporaries, the memoirs of H. Madaminova contains accurate information. In particular, Hassan Khan Madaminov "*Исломхўжа мамлакат тариаққиётига қадим бўлиб, Хоразм аҳолиси турмушини ўзгартирмак мақсади ила Хасан Муҳаммад бий билан бирликда тоза қонун тузиб, 10 моддадан иборат дастурамал ишлаб чиқорди*"³.

In 1910, the Prime Minister of Khiva, Islamkhoja, proposed to Khan a plan for reforms of the socio-economic life of the state. This direct management is connected with the tax system and finances, and the program provides for the formation of the state budget, the establishment of taxes in a certain order, the termination of work duties, the elimination of their career abuses by assigning officials a clearly defined salary, the opening of hospitals and schools, spending funds from taxes on the development of the country.

The first chapter of the reform program was called "giving officials salary". It is known that officials such as Mehtar, Koshbegi, Devonbegi, due to their Devonian origin, participated in the tax system of the Khanate of Khiva. They were given a monthly salary, and a certain part of the taxes collected went to pay for housing and coinage. They also received tax benefits. The reform introduces a procedure for setting salaries in accordance with the position of an official.

² Central Archive of Republic of Uzbekistan, fond I-125, opis' 1, No 291

³ Central Archive of Republic of Uzbekistan, fond I-125, opis' 1, No 609

According to him, the highest officials of the state are paid from 5 thousand to 10 thousand. tillos per year, and for junior officials - from 1 to 2 thousand tillos⁴.

Also in the khanate, palace officials, who were considered large landowners, criticized the need to revise tarkhan labels and some tax benefits that exempt from all types of taxes, as well as the idea of abolishing privileges to form a fair tax system.

Chapter 2 of the reform program concerned land ownership and taxes, and instead of levying a categorical tax, the lie was levied depending on the yield of arable land. The procedure for taxing fertile arable land in the amount of 9 coins per tanobi hisob and in the amount of 7 coins per tanob of low-income land has been established⁵.

The labor service in the agriculture of the Khiva Khanate was replaced by the begar system. According to the new decree, forced labor was prohibited, and a fee of 2 coins per day was introduced for a 12-day commitment to khazu, 1 person from every 10 Su lands to clean and repair irrigation networks from turbulence⁶.

Prior to this event, which was held with the aim of restoring social justice, Yof qazu was granted the status of maof for a fee and was relieved of work duties for a year. According to X. Madaminov's quote, 16,000 khazuvchi's were employed annually in Pahlavon Yofi, maofilda for high-ranking officials, sipokhi lands and a certain fee, and 5 000-6 000 qazuvchi's were registered as bikazu, the rest of the qazuvchi's were also forced to go about their business.

Chapter 3 of the reform program dealt with the issue of tax deductions levied on representatives of trade and industry. But the fact that zakat and market fees under the reform program were obtained on the basis of Sharia by officials at a council held in the Khan's Palace in 1911 at the request of merchants, left unchanged.

Chapter 4 of the program is aimed at regulating various payments and fees in the markets, and prescribes to receive moinat in large stores in 3 tillo, in nettle - in 1 tillo. There will also be a tax deduction in the amount of half a penny to three coins from each cattle brought to the markets for sale⁷.

Within the framework of the reform program promoted by Islamkhoja, issues of road repair, construction of new modern bridges, land remeasurement

⁴ Historical museum Khiva № 36/87

⁵ А.Садуллаев, А.Сотликов, О.Абдуллаев., Сайид Исломхужа (Сиёсий, маданий-маърифий фаолияти) – Т.2005

⁶ Central Archive of Republic of Uzbekistan, fond I-125, opis' 1, No 609

⁷ М.Н.Ниязатов., Поиск консенсуса. Российско-хивинские геополитические отношения в XVI – начале XX в. – СПб., 2010. С.496

and reorganization of land irrigation procedures, regulation of waqf ownership, and improvement of school activities were raised.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the above sources shows that the economy of the Khiva Khanate at the beginning of the 20th century remained in a difficult situation and needed reforms. In this context, the program of Islamic reforms is important for its time and is aimed at improving the life of society and gives its positive result.

Firstly, as a result of reducing the type of tax in the country and increasing the amount of tax levied on wealthy members of the nobility, together with the income of the population, this led to an increase in revenues to the treasury of the country.

Secondly, due to the introduction of a certain payment of a hack in exchange for their labor, as well as the introduction of a procedure for their release from it for a certain fee, instead of attracting the population to forced labor, the principles of positive justice are improved among the population.

Thirdly, he built new-style schools, madrassas, in exchange for income from taxes levied. In exchange for improving education and the educational system, further training of Khiva youth abroad will be established.

Fourthly, thanks to the special funds and attention paid to the repair or reconstruction of roads and bridges in the country, the work of merchants and local residents arriving in the country is facilitated for a while. This in itself contributed to the development of trade.

As a conclusion, we can say that the reforms carried out a century ago led to certain positive changes in the life of the state and society. Today, the reforms carried out with the aim of further improving the socio-economic life of the state are appropriate and relevant.

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